

**Study on the Concept of Ideal Systems, Ideal
Technology and their Realization Opportunities
using ICCT & Nanotechnology**

SYNOPSIS

**of
the Thesis to be submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the
Degree of**

DOCTOR OF SCIENCE (D. Sc.)

In the Area of Technology Management

By

Dr. P. SREERAMANA AITHAL

**M.Sc. (Physics), M.Sc. (E-Business), M.I.T (I.T.), M.Tech. (I.T.),
Ph.D.(Physics), Ph.D.(Business Management),
PostDoc. @ PRL, Ahmedabad; PostDoc. @ CREOL, UCF, USA.
Professor, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA.**

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mukka- 574146, Mangalore, Karnataka State, INDIA

November 2020

SYNOPSIS

TOPIC OF THE THESIS

Study on the Concept of Ideal Systems, Ideal Technology, and their Realization Opportunities using ICCT & Nanotechnology

Systems and Technology are two interconnected issues in scientific society. The developments and progress in society depend on the improvements in the performance of every system and innovations in technology. It is believed that the performance of a system and the capability of technology can be continuously improved by means of comparing their properties with the properties of an ideal system or ideal technology, respectively. Research in any system or technology is basically generating *new knowledge* based on intensive study of existing systems or technology and any concepts/issues/problems related to them. Research is also defined as a *new interpretation* of existing knowledge about any issues/concepts/solutions of the problems of any system or technology by means of analysing them using a suitable framework.

Technology is used in many ways to solve many complicated challenges in society. Certain technologies have grown and expanded their branches to many areas and sectors of practice in such a way that they have been designated as General-Purpose Technologies. General Purpose Technologies' (GPT) are characterized by pervasiveness, where they have an inherent potential for technical improvements, and innovation complementarities, meaning that productivity through research and development in related sectors increases due to the consequence of innovative applications through such general-purpose technologies. Thus, as general-purpose technologies progress, they spread throughout the economy, eventually bringing about generalized productivity gains. Examples include the steam engine, railroad, interchangeable parts, electricity, electronics, material handling, mechanization, control theory (automation), the automobile, the computer, the Internet, and nanotechnology. In the first chapter, we have identified, analysed, and compared Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT), and Nanotechnology (NT) as the two most important general-purpose technologies due to their abilities to solve both basic problems and advanced need of society. The first chapter also contains a conceptual and predictive proposal on how various general-purpose technologies including ICCT and NT are potentially contributing toward creating a techno-society and based on further progress and spread of such technologies to every dimension of human life to reach the ultimate level of civilization in or

around this earth. The analysis finally leads to the development of the concept of ‘Universal Technology’ model.

Ideal properties of a device or a system can be used to upgrade or improve its properties toward reaching 100% efficiency. By comparing the properties/characteristics of a practical device/system with its ideal counterpart, one can find out the possible modifications in that device /system toward reaching the objective of achieving such an ideal system. Even though ideal systems are hypothetical systems which cannot be realized completely in practice, they give a broad idea of how practical systems can be improved continuously to reach ideal system characteristics. The ideal system characteristics of technology, business, education, banking, software, computing, and drug are discussed in this Thesis, under input characteristics, system characteristics, output characteristics, and external characteristics shows an opportunity to the scientists and engineers to develop and improve such practical systems further with an objective to reach the goal. The Thesis also focuses on how to improve the existing systems toward the ideal level by using two well-known general purpose and universal technologies of ICCT and NT.

The objective of the present research is to study the characteristics of some of the ideal systems and comparing these ideal characteristics with characteristics of practical systems with the intention of possible improvements using current and future technologies. The research includes the management of nanotechnology innovations in automobiles and renewable energy sectors and a model of commercialization of nanotechnology products & services. It also includes the analysis of some of these systems using our newly developed analysis method called ABCD framework.

The research work is designed to predict ideal characteristics of some systems and comparison with corresponding practical systems which include : (1) Ideal technology and comparison with nanotechnology, (2) Ideal water purifier and comparison with nanotechnology based water purifier system, (3) Ideal business and comparison with mobile business, (4) Ideal Education System and its realization opportunity using ICCT, (5) Ideal drug system and its realization opportunity using nanopharmaceutical science, (6) Ideal Banking System and its realization opportunity using mobile banking technology, (7) Ideal Software System and its realization opportunity using universal automation system, and (8) Ideal computing system and its realization opportunity using Cloud computing system. Some of the potential technologies proposed to improve the current systems toward ideal systems are analysed using a suitable framework to interpret the abilities of these technologies to improve the performance of the systems.

The research methodology is qualitative in nature, including the development of conceptual ideal system models and prediction of ideal characteristics using qualitative data collection instrument, namely focus group method. It also includes the identification of suitable breakthrough technologies of the 21st century, analyzing them for realizing or improving practical systems toward ideal systems of a chosen type. Accordingly, various hypothetical ideal systems including : Ideal technology and comparison with nanotechnology, Ideal water purifier and comparison with nanotechnology based water purifier system, Ideal business and comparison with mobile business, Ideal Education System and its realization opportunities using ICCT, Ideal drug system and its realization opportunity using nanopharmaceutical science, Ideal Banking System and its realization opportunity using mobile banking technology, Ideal Software System and its realization opportunity using universal automation system, and Ideal computing system and its realization opportunity using Cloud computing system are predicted and suitable innovative technologies to manage and improve corresponding practical systems are identified and analyzed for further research. The research methodology also includes the management of business strategies of nanotechnology products and services in different industries including innovations in automobiles sector and renewable energy sectors is discussed and a new model of commercialization of nanotechnology products & services is also proposed. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages are analysed for the nanotechnology as universal technology and green technology to solve many basic and advanced problems of society for living comfortable life using a new self-developed analysing framework called ABCD Analysis Framework. Using the framework, the Factor & Elemental analysis is carried out for Nanotechnology as Green Technology and the results are depicted. This conceptual qualitative research is concluded by interpreting the possible combined potential of two Universal Technologies - Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) and Nanotechnology (NT) in taking the world toward the so called '*Technology based Singularity*' and '*Human Immortality*'.

Chapter 1 contains a discussion on various General-Purpose Technologies and their contributions toward developing Sustainable Society, and two prominent general-purpose technologies, which are very active currently identified as Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) and Nanotechnology (NT) and their expected abilities to change the world and possible contributions toward further progressed civilian society are discussed. Chapter 1 also contains the research objective, research design, and research methodology used in the Thesis. The Thesis contains the results of the quantitative research

carried out on new conceptual models developed and new interpretation made on a systematic interpretation.

Chapter 2 contains an elaborate review of various ideal system models used to improve the characteristics of practical systems, anticipated breakthrough technologies of 21st century, and nanotechnology innovations & business opportunities : a review on how technology has affected society and its surroundings in a number of ways. In many societies, technology has helped to develop more advanced economies (including today's global economy) and has supported the rise of leisure class people. The concept of the ideal engine, ideal switch, ideal semiconductor devices like ideal diodes, transistors, etc. have been defined and taken as standards to improve the quality and performance of such practical devices or systems. It is found that, by keeping such a hypothetical device or systems in mind, researchers have to continuously improve the characteristics/properties of practical devices/systems to upgrade their performances. Hence, ideal properties of a device or a system can be used to upgrade or improve its properties toward reaching 100% efficiency. By comparing the properties/characteristics of a practical device/system with its ideal counterpart, one can find out the possible modifications in that device/system toward reaching the objective of achieving such an ideal device. In this chapter, we have developed the concept of Ideal technology by creating a model and identified its important characteristics. These characteristics are grouped into four categories namely input conditions, output conditions, system conditions and environmental conditions/social expectations. These characteristics are further discussed, analyzed and compared with present technologies. Based on the discussion, it is realized that many of the characteristics of the ideal technology are achievable through discoveries and innovations in Nanotechnology. Finally, the characteristics of this ideal technology model are compared with nanotechnology developments and the possible way of realizing nanotechnology as ideal technology is discussed.

Chapter 3 contains the concept of ideal technology and its realization opportunity using nanotechnology, opportunities & challenges for green technology in 21st century, concept of ideal water purifier system to produce potable water and its realization opportunities using nanotechnology, and nanotechnological innovations & business environment for automobile sector : a futuristic approach, nanotechnology innovations & business opportunities in renewable energy sector, concept & characteristics of ideal energy system and its realization constraints, realization opportunity of ideal energy system using nanotechnology based

research and innovations and the concept of ideal drug & its realization opportunity using present pharmaceutical sciences scenario.

In chapter 4, the concept of an ideal business model & its realization opportunity using E-Business model is discussed. The chapter also contains the suggestion as mobile business as an optimum model for ideal business, business strategy for nanotechnology based products & services, and nanotechnology innovations and commercialization – opportunities, challenges & reasons for delay along with a new model for the commercialization of nanotechnology products and services are proposed and analysed.

In chapter 5, the concept and characteristics of the ideal education system and its realization opportunity through online open education model using mobile devices are proposed and analysed. The chapter also consists of discussion on the impact of On-line education on higher education system and how Smart Library Model can be used as Universal Library for future generation education systems.

Chapter 6 contains the concept of ideal banking, its characteristics, realization of ideal banking concept based on ubiquitous banking using mobile devices, and a comparison of the ideal banking model with the mobile banking system.

In chapter 7, the concept of ideal software, its realization scenarios, and opportunity for realizing the ideal computing system using cloud computing model are proposed, discussed and analysed.

In chapter 8, a new ABCD technique to analyse business models, concepts, technology, systems, and strategies is proposed, developed, and used to analyse nanotechnology as green technology. The chapter also contains the Factor & Elemental Analysis of nanotechnology as green technology using ABCD framework.

Finally, in chapter 9, the summary of the work on ideal systems, ideal technology, and Nanotechnology based innovations for human life comfortability are discussed with a question to analyse – Are we marching toward technological immortality ?

The entire Thesis is based on the concept of a unique research model to identify the gap between ideal system/technology and present system/technology and to identify opportunities to minimize the gap to improve the system/technology toward ideal level. In this effort, many new system and technology models with ideal characteristics are proposed and a new system/technology analysis framework called ABCD analysis method is developed and used to analyse nanotechnology as green technology.

The Thesis highlights the importance of two general purpose technologies including ICCT and NT, which are emerging as “Universal Technologies” in solving many problems in society to provide a comfortable life to every human being with the slogan in Sanskrit “Sarve Janaha Sukhino Bhavanthu”. The Thesis also analyses and interpret how the advancements in nanotechnology help to solve basic problems to provide nutritious food, potable water, renewable energy, comfortable health to all human beings in society. The research work also anticipates and discusses the possibilities of how health science progress will be driven by nanotechnology-based innovations leading to predict and most desired immortality of living beings in this world and reaching the expected status – the ultimate state in human life comfortability.

The Thesis is prepared by combining the 30 published papers under the single Project “**Ideal Systems and Realization Opportunity**” on the broad area of ‘**Technology Management**’. This post-doctoral project includes both aspects of research - creating new knowledge and new interpretation of existing knowledge through systematic analysis.

Published Papers Considered Chapter wise :

Chapter 1 : Introduction

(1) **Aithal, P. S.** and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal. (2018). Study of various General-Purpose Technologies and their contribution towards developing Sustainable Society. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 3(2), 16-33. ISSN : 2581-6012, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.1409476>.

Chapter 2 : Review on Ideal Systems & Technology

(2) **Aithal, P. S.** (2016). Review on Various Ideal System Models Used to Improve the Characteristics of Practical Systems. *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research*, ISSN: 2456 – 3080, 1(1), 47-56. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.159749>.

(3) **Aithal, P. S.**, Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2015). A review on Anticipated Breakthrough Technologies of 21st Century. *International Journal of Research & Development in Technology and Management Sciences*, 21(6), 112 – 133. ISBN - 1-63102-450-7, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61617>.

(4) **Aithal, P. S.** (January 2016). Nanotechnology Innovations & Business Opportunities : A Review. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 182-204. ISSN: 2249-0558, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161153>.

Chapter 3 : Ideal Technology & Its Realization Opportunity

(5) **Aithal, P. S.**, & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2015). Ideal Technology Concept & its Realization Opportunity using Nanotechnology, *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAIEEM)*, 4(2), 153 – 164. ISSN: 2319-4847. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61591>.

(6) **Aithal, P. S.** and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2016). Opportunities & Challenges for Green Technology in 21st Century. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 818-828. ISSN: 2455–5428. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.62020>.

(7) Shubhrajyotsna Aithal & **Aithal, P. S.** (2018). Concept of Ideal Water Purifier System to Produce Potable Water and its Realization Opportunities using Nanotechnology. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 2(2), 8-26. ISSN: 2581-7000, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1323714>.

(8) **Aithal, P. S.** & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2016). Nanotechnological Innovations & Business Environment for Indian Automobile Sector : A Futuristic Approach. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 296-307. ISSN: 2455–5630, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161090>.

(9) **Aithal, P. S.** & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2016). Nanotechnology Innovations & Business Opportunities in Renewable Energy Sector. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 1(1), 674- 692. ISSN: 2455–4200. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160905>.

(10) **Aithal, P. S.** & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2018). The Concept & Characteristics of Ideal Energy System and its Realization Constraints. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 2(2), 127-137. ISSN: 2581-7000, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1487702>.

(11) Shubhrajyotsna Aithal & **Aithal, P. S.** (2018). The Realization Opportunity of Ideal Energy System using Nanotechnology Based Research and Innovations. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology*, 3(2), 1-15., ISSN: 2456 – 4664. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2531876>.

(12) Architha Aithal & **Aithal, P.S.** (2018). The concept of Ideal Drug & Its Realization Opportunity using present Pharmaceutical Sciences Scenario. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Pharmacy (IJHSP)*, 2(2), 11-26. ISSN: 2581-6411, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1469963>.

Chapter 4 :Ideal Business System & Its Realization Opportunity

- (13) **Aithal, P. S.** (2015). Concept of Ideal Business & Its Realization Using E-Business Model. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 4(3), 1267 – 1274. ISSN: 2319-7064, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61648>.
- (14) **Aithal, P. S.** (2015). Mobile Business as an Optimum Model for Ideal Business. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 146-159, (July 2015), ISSN: 2249-0558, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163880>.
- (15) **Aithal P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal** (2016). Business Strategy for Nanotechnology based Products & Services. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR)*, 5(4), 139-149, ISSN : 2226-8235. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161127>.
- (16) **Aithal, P. S. and Shubrajyotsna Aithal** (2016). Nanotechnology Innovations and Commercialization – Opportunities, Challenges & Reasons for Delay. *International Journal of Engineering and Manufacturing (IJEM)*, 6(6), 15-25, ISSN: 2305-3631. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161161>, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5815/ijem.2016.06.02>.
- (17) **Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal** (2016). A New Model for Commercialization of Nanotechnology Products and Services. *International Journal of Computational Research and Development*, 1(1), 84-93. ISSN: 2456–3137. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163536>.

Chapter 5 :Ideal Education System & Its Realization Opportunity

- (18) **Aithal P. S. and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal** (2014). Ideal education system and its realization through online education model using mobile devices, *Proceedings of IISRO Multi Conference 2014*, Bangkok, 7/01/2014, 140 - 146, ISBN No. 978-81-927104-33-13. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.62059>.
- (19) **Aithal P. S. and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal** (2015). An Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 3(3), 2464 - 2469. ISSN: 2321-3418, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61654>.
- (20) **Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal**, (2016). Impact of On-line Education on Higher Education System. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 1(1), 225-235. ISSN: 2455 – 4200. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161113>.
- (21) **Aithal, P. S.** (2016). Smart Library Model for Future Generations. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 1(1), 693-703. ISSN: 2455 – 4200. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160904>.

Chapter 6 :Ideal Banking System & Its Realization Opportunity

- (22) **Aithal, P. S.** (2016). Ideal Banking Concept and Characteristics. *International Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences (IRJMIS)*, 3(11), 46-55. ISSN: 2395-7492, DOI : <http://dx.doi.org/10.21744/irjmis.v3i11.311>.

(23) **Aithal, P. S.** (2016). Realization of Ideal Banking Concept using Ubiquitous Banking, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(2),119-135. ISSN: 2455 - 5630, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.164703>.

(24) **Aithal, P. S.** (2016). A Comparison of Ideal Banking Model with Mobile Banking System. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(2), 206-224. ISSN: 2455- 5428, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.198708>.

Chapter 7 :Ideal Software System & Its Realization Opportunity

(25) **Aithal, P. S., & Vaikuth Pai, T.,** (2016). Concept of Ideal Software and its Realization Scenarios. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 826-837. ISSN : 2455-5630, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160908>.

(26) **Aithal, P. S. & Priyesh Pai, T.** (2017). Opportunity for Realizing Ideal Computing System using Cloud Computing Model. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(2), 60-71. ISSN: 2581-6942, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1094995>.

Chapter 8 : Analysis of Systems Using ABCD Frameworks

(27) **Aithal, P. S., V.T. Shailashree, Suresh Kumar, P. M.** (2015). A New ABCD Technique to Analyze Business Models & Concepts. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(4), 409 – 423. ISSN: 2249-0558, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61652>.

(28) **Aithal, P. S.** (2016). Study on ABCD Analysis Technique for Business Models, business strategies, Operating Concepts & Business Systems. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 98-115. ISSN: 2321-1784, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161137>.

(29) **Aithal P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal** (2018). Factor & Elemental Analysis of Nanotechnology as Green Technology using ABCD Framework. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 3(2), 57-72. ISSN : 2581-6012. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1451490>.

Chapter 9 : Conclusion

(30) **Aithal P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal** (2018). Nanotechnology based Innovations and Human Life Comfortability –Are we Marching towards Immortality ? *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 2(2), 71-86. ISSN: 2582-7000, DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1451498>.

Dr. P. S. Aithal
Date : 11/11/2020
